

FAILURE PROBABILITY OF PIN JOINT IN CFRP LAMINATE

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Abstract

Composite materials have more scattering properties and complicated fracture modes than conventional metals. Therefore the designs of composite structures are tend to be conservative in deterministic design process. This paper applies a probabilistic approach to pin joints in composite laminates, which combines strength analyses by finite element method and Monte Carlo simulation utilizing Response Surface Method. Frictions between the loading pins and the fastener holes in CFRP laminates are taken account into the FE analyses. Probabilistic strength of the joint is estimated and the probabilistic and deterministic designs are compared and discussed.

Keywords: *Joints, Probabilistic design and analysis, Response surface method*

1 Introduction

Nowadays, wind turbines are receiving many attentions as a source of renewable energy. The blades of the turbines are required to be lightweight for generation efficiency. Therefore many of them are made from composite materials. The composite materials, however, have more scattering material properties than conventional metals. So the designs of composite structures, e.g. wind turbine blades and aircrafts, generally tend to be conservative and result in heavier designs than expectations. Therefore Probabilistic Design and Analysis (PDA) method [1, 2] has been applied to develop more efficient designs of composite structures. In this study, an approach combining finite element damage analyses and a stochastic technique was applied to pin joints in CFRP laminates to analyze the probabilistic strength of the joints. The finite element analyses take account of frictional contacts between the fastener hole in the CFRP specimen and the loading pin made of steel.

The joint have various design parameters. This paper treats two groups; strengths and dimensions. Strength parameters inherent in the material itself and controllable dimension parameters were evaluated and compared for their effects on the strength. At last, the deterministic and probabilistic designs are compared and discussed.

2 Analysis

2.1 Finite Element Model

This paper deals the bearing test[3] as an example of typical mechanical joints for composites and Fig. 1 shows a simplified image of the test. The CFRP specimen has a hole, and a tensile load is applied through the loading pin. The case of pinned joint (not bolted) is treated in this study. The pinned joints have no out-of-plane constraint so that the failure condition mainly depends on material properties more than the bolted joints. Extensometers were equipped on both edges of the specimen to measure displacements. And a 2D finite element model of the CFRP pin joint is presented in Fig. 2. The model was constructed in ANSYS ver. 12.1 software. The dimension of the model is based on a testing standard[3]. The specimen has a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_s$. Material properties of a lamina are based on the TR50S/#1053I prepreg[4]. And the loading pin is assumed as an elastic body corresponding to steel. Contact elements are aligned between the pin and hole in the specimen. And each element has a different coefficient of friction (as a material constant). because the coefficients have a dependency on the fiber orientation. Therefore the equivalent coefficients of friction on the contact surface need to be calculated. This process is referred in the next section.

2.2 Effective friction coefficient on laminate edges

The calculation in this section is based on a theory in reference[5]. In the reference, a Finite Element analysis was performed to acquire a numerical solution. However the FE analysis is converted as an analysis by classical laminate theory in this paper.

The laminate is assumed having a symmetrical stacking sequence consisting of $2n$ plies (Fig. 3). The equivalent coefficient of friction on the laminate edge, μ_c is defined as;

$$\mu_c = \frac{N_{xy}}{N_y} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{2n} (z_{k+1} - z_k) \tau_{xy}^{(k)}}{\sum_{k=1}^{2n} (z_{k+1} - z_k) \sigma_y^{(k)}} \quad (1)$$

N_{xy} , N_y are resultant stresses. Superscript (k) denotes the quantity in the k th ply. Then next relationship is assumed, based on Coulomb's friction law, as follows:

$$\tau_{xy}^{(k)} = \mu^{(k)} \sigma_y^{(k)} \quad (2)$$

where $\mu^{(k)}$ is a friction coefficient in the edge of the k th ply. Substituting Eq (2) into Eq. (1);

$$\mu_c = \frac{N_{xy}}{N_y} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{2n} (z_{k+1} - z_k) \mu^{(k)} \sigma_y^{(k)}}{\sum_{k=1}^{2n} (z_{k+1} - z_k) \sigma_y^{(k)}} \quad (3)$$

Next, consider a laminate under the load condition depicted in Fig. 4. P in the figure is a load per unit width. The condition is equivalent to the case in which compressive and frictional loads are applied to an edge of a laminate whose friction coefficient is equal to μ_c . The constitutive equation of the laminate is;

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{ij} & b_{ij} \\ b_{ij} & d_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ -P \\ \mu_c P \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ b & d \end{bmatrix}$ is a compliance matrix of the laminate. Eq. (4) is written down with respect to strains, ε_x , ε_y and γ_{xy} and ε_x and γ_{xy} are able to be expressed using ε_y ;

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x &= \frac{a_{12} - a_{16}\mu_c}{a_{22} - a_{26}\mu_c} \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} &= \frac{a_{62} - a_{66}\mu_c}{a_{22} - a_{26}\mu_c} \varepsilon_y \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Substituting Eq. (5) into stress - strain relation in the k th ply (Eq. (6)), Eq. (7) is acquired. The Stress $\sigma_y^{(k)}$ is represented by a function of μ_c , $f_y(\mu_c)$ and strain, ε_y (in [5], finite element method was performed to acquire this $\sigma_y^{(k)} - \varepsilon_y$ relation);

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x^{(k)} \\ \sigma_y^{(k)} \\ \tau_{xy}^{(k)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11}^{(k)} & \bar{S}_{12}^{(k)} & \bar{S}_{16}^{(k)} \\ \bar{S}_{21}^{(k)} & \bar{S}_{22}^{(k)} & \bar{S}_{26}^{(k)} \\ \bar{S}_{61}^{(k)} & \bar{S}_{62}^{(k)} & \bar{S}_{66}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y^{(k)} &= \bar{S}_{21}^{(k)} \varepsilon_x + \bar{S}_{22}^{(k)} \varepsilon_y + \bar{S}_{26}^{(k)} \gamma_{xy} \\ &= \left(\bar{S}_{21}^{(k)} \frac{a_{12} - a_{16}\mu_c}{a_{22} - a_{26}\mu_c} + \bar{S}_{22}^{(k)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \bar{S}_{26}^{(k)} \frac{a_{62} - a_{66}\mu_c}{a_{22} - a_{26}\mu_c} \right) \varepsilon_y \\ &= f_y(\mu_c) \varepsilon_y \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

After substituting Eq. (7), Eq. (3) can be transformed;

$$\frac{\sum_{k=1}^{2n} (z_{k+1} - z_k) \mu^{(k)} f_y(\mu_c)}{\sum_{k=1}^{2n} (z_{k+1} - z_k) f_y(\mu_c)} - \mu_c = 0 \quad (8)$$

The equivalent coefficient of friction, μ_c can be calculated as a solution of the above nonlinear equation.

$\mu^{(k)}$ is assumed to be given as a linear function of fiber orientation of the k th ply, $\theta^{(k)}$ [rad];

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^{(k)} &= a\theta^{(k)} + b \\ a &= 0.139, b = 0.142 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The constants, a and b were determined on the basis of an experimental result with respect to unidirectional off-axis laminates[5, 6].

A computed distribution of μ_c on contact edge is shown in Fig. 4. To solve the Eq. (7), bisection method algorithm was utilized. The semicircle on the edge of the fastener hole is divided into 32 elements. μ_c for each element is that at the center of the element. The distribution have peaks at 0, 45, 90, 135 and 180 deg. Especially, elements around 45 and 135 deg are loaded high shear stress compared to others.

2.3 Design Variables

Design variables of the joint were classified into two groups, strengths and shape parameters. The strength parameters are compressive strength in longitudinal direction of a lamina, L_c and in-plane shear strength, S . The shape parameter is the hole diameter, D_h . Other parameters (elastic constants etc.) are assumed negligible because of their small variability and/or small effect on the bearing behavior. Table 1 contains the levels of the 3 design variables. The levels of D_h were set on the basis of its prescribed design tolerances [3]. The minimum and maximum levels of L_c and S were intended to correspond to $\mu - 3\sigma$ and $\mu + 3\sigma$, respectively assuming 5% standard deviation (μ : mean value and σ : standard deviation). The combinations of the levels were input to the FE model. Then failure analyses were performed and joint strengths (bearing strengths), F_b were calculated. Therefore total 100 (= 4 x 5 x 5) finite element analyses would be executed.

2.4 Failure Analyses

An incremental displacement load is applied to the specimen until the bearing load drops. Fig. 6 is a typical bearing stress – strain relationship during the sequence. Initial linear section of the curve was omitted and its peak is magnified. The definitions of bearing stress and strain are;

$$\sigma_b = \frac{P}{D_h h} \quad (10)$$

$$\varepsilon_b = \frac{U}{D_h} \quad (11)$$

where P is the bearing load, h is thickness of the laminate and U is an average of displacements measured by the two extensometers. In the finite element analyses, U was replaced by average displacement of nodal points locating at the extensometer position of the bearing test. Due to failures of elements near the contact area, bearing stiffness is reduced and finally the load drop happens. The maximum bearing stress in the curve is defined as bearing strength, F_b .

To judge if an element is failed, 4-mode Hashin criterion[7] was adopted and the damage of the element is expressed as degradations in elastic constants. If an element is failed in fibrous modes (in tension or compression), all of moduli (E_L , E_T and G_{LT}) are reduced into 1% value of their originals. In matrix modes, only E_T and G_{LT} are reduced[8].

To detect a peak in the stress–strain curve precisely, the increment of displacement was varied according to predetermined values (0.010 → 0.00333 → 0.00111 → 0.00037 mm).

The 100 analyses were performed according to the combinations of the design parameters to survey the behavior of the analysis against to the variations of the variables.

2.5 Response Surface Equation

The behavior of the FE failure analysis is emulated by a polynomial called Response Surface, RS equation (Eq. (12)) which had the normalized design parameters, which were converted to have ranges of -1.0 ~ +1.0 and “*” denotes the normalized one of the variable itself.

$$\begin{aligned} F_b = & a_0 + a_1 D_h^* + a_2 S^* + a_3 D_h^* S^* \\ & + a_4 L_c^* S^* + a_5 D_h^{*2} + a_6 S^{*2} \\ & + a_7 D_h^{*2} L_c^* + a_8 D_h^{*2} S^* \\ & + a_9 L_c^{*2} S^* + a_{10} D_h^* S^{*2} \\ & + a_{11} L_c^* S^{*2} + a_{12} D_h^{*2} S^{*2} \\ & + a_{13} L_c^{*2} S^{*2} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

We confirmed the form of Eq. (12) fits the behavior of the FE analysis most. The coefficients, $a_0 \sim a_{13}$ were determined to minimize the square sum of the residual errors (Table 2). Its adjusted coefficient of

determination, R_{ad}^2 is 95%. All of the coefficients ensured to have significances by t -test.

“Sensitivity” represents quantification of an effect of a variable (one of the design parameters) on a property (the joint strength, F_b) and can be expressed as a partial differential with respect to the variable. If the sensitivities are evaluated when all variables have their mean values (normalized mean values are 0.0), the coefficients a_1 and a_2 suggest the sensitivities of D_h^* and S^* (a coefficient for 1st order term of L_c^* is regarded as insignificant through t -test but interaction terms still remain). The result shows that the bearing strength, F_b is more affected by the strength parameters S^* than the shape parameters D_h^* .

2.6 Monte Carlo Simulation

Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) was performed to reveal the stochastic properties of the joint. Normalized strength parameters, L_c^* and S^* are assumed as normal random variables (mean: 0.0, S.D.: 0.33). Normalized diameter of the fastener hole, D_h^* is assumed an uniform random variable whose range is [-1.0, +1.0]. The number of trials for the MCS was set to 10000 times.

Fig. 7 shows the result of the MCS in histogram and probability density function forms. The results could be applied into a 3-parameter Weibull distribution (shape parameter, α : 1.85 MPa, scale, β : 60.6 MPa and location, γ : 430 MPa each) by χ^2 test. Its standard deviation is able to be computed from the parameters; S.D. = 30.2 MPa. Compared to an actual test, in which S.D. = 23.9 MPa, the analytical result shows a similar scatter of the bearing strength. In Fig. 8, probabilistic and deterministic designs were compared. The graph has probability of failure and bearing stress σ_b as vertical and horizontal axes each. The curve is the cumulative density function of F_b . Starting from the left, the vertical lines indicate the values at M.S. = 0.5, probability of failure, $p.o.f.$ = 10^{-8} and Design tolerance (deterministic strength) respectively. The design tolerance is acquired from the following definition; “A-value” which can be regarded that 99% of population is contained with 95% reliability level in a range greater than the value, assuming normal distribution. M.S. means Margin of Safety which indicates a margin the joint has against its limiting load. The design tolerance is correspond to M.S. = 0.0 which means that the limiting load is

equal to the deterministic strength of the joint. The figure shows that the designs of “M.S. = 0.0” and “M.S. = 0.5” have 0 probability of failure. This is owing to the applied Weibull distribution, which has a lower boundary. Probabilistic Design and Analysis method would help to prevent the composite design from being too conservative.

3. Conclusion

The strength of pin joints in CFRP laminates was analyzed probabilistically. In failure analysis, the friction behavior between the fastener hole and the loading pin was considered. The dependency of the strength on design factors was evaluated. Shear strength suggests strong effect on the strength of the joint. The stochastic property of the strength was calculated by Monte Carlo simulation and the probability of failure and margin of safety were interrelated.

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Table 1 Table of Levels

Lv.	1	2	3	4	5
D_h [mm]	6.00	6.01	6.02	6.03	-
L_c [MPa]	1275	1388	1500	1613	1725
S [MPa]	85.0	92.5	100.0	107.5	115.0

Table 2 Coefficients of the RS equation [MPa]

i	0	1	2	3
a_i	463	8.80	81.4	10.3
i	4	5	6	7
a_i	23.4	48.7	52.2	7.50
i	8	9	10	11
a_i	-9.73	-16.6	-17.8	21.0
i	12	13		
a_i	-48.5	-19.1		

Fig. 1 Schematic of the bearing test

Fig. 2 Finite element model of the composite pin joint

Fig. 3 Coordinate system on laminate edge

Fig. 4 Considered load condition for the friction problem

Fig. 5
Distribution of the friction coefficient on fastener hole edge

Fig. 7 Monte Carlo simulation result

Fig. 6
An example of bearing stress – strain curves in damage progress analysis ($D_h = 6.010$ mm, $L_c = 1500$ MPa, $S = 100$ MPa)

Fig. 8 Probabilistic bearing strength